

Microwave and conventional sintering of SiC/SiC composites:

Fracture behaviors and microstructures

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Abstract

SiC_f/SiC composites were fabricated by polymer impregnation and pyrolysis (PIP) process via microwave or conventional heating at 800°C, 900°C, 1000°C and 1100°C, respectively. The results indicate that the microwave sintered SiC_f/SiC composites have better flexural properties than the conventional sintered ones at the same sintering temperature, as well as their higher strain values and wider fluctuating plateaus than the conventional ones on the typical load-displacement curves. The different fracture behaviors are owing to their different microstructures of the fabricated SiC/SiC composites. It is observed by scanning electron microscopy that, resulting from a faster heating rate (~40°C/min), the microwave heating sintered

SiC/SiC composites have more micro-cracks on the fiber bundle surface, and looser matrix intra the fiber bundles than the conventional heating sintered products.

Keywords: Microwave sintering; SiC/SiC; Fracture behavior; Microstructure

1. Introduction

SiC/SiC composites have got much attention for their excellent mechanical properties and thermal stability, making them the promising candidate materials in aerospace vehicles, fusion energy systems and other high temperature structural applications. PIP and Chemical Vapor Infiltration (CVI) are two of the most common ways to fabricate SiC matrix composites. By contrast, PIP process can be applied to make large-scale components with complex shapes, so it is considered to be a more effective routine to fabricate SiC/SiC composites. But the intrinsic limitations, such as high process temperature, lengthy pyrolysis cycles and high cost, have restricted its application and development [1-3].

Due to the remarkable features, such as rapid heating rates, low process temperature and tailored material properties, microwave heating technique provides a novel routing to overcome the above drawbacks of PIP process [2, 4-12]. Although the research is still on a starting stage, the advantages of the microwave heating are quite notable. For example, S.M. Dong *et al.* [2] pointed out that the fracture behaviors can be modified by preparing 2D SiC/SiC composites using the microwave heating. H.S. Park *et al.* [12] indicated that the microwave heating rates of the pyrolysis of carbon fiber reinforced plastics can be up to $\sim 33^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, and the energy saving rates of 25%-70 % are possible.

H.Y. Yang *et al.* [13] have studied the changing tendency of the flexural properties of the microwave and conventional heating sintered SiC/SiC composites fabricated from 800°C to 1200°C, and proved that microwave heating sintered SiC/SiC composites have better flexural properties than the conventional heating sintered ones. But the respective fracture behaviors of the microwave and conventional heating sintered SiC/SiC composites have not been involved. Therefore, we aim to investigate them in this paper.

2. Experimental procedure

KD-I SiC fiber bundles (characteristics listed in [14]) were braided into three-dimension and four-direction preforms (fiber volume fraction ~45%), coated with pyrolytic carbon (PyC) as interface layers. Polycarbosilane (PCS, provided by National University of Defense Technology, China) with xylene as a solvent was applied as the polymer precursor of the SiC matrix. SiC fiber preforms were then impregnated with PCS solution by vacuum infiltration and then pyrolyzed by the conventional and microwave heating for 15 cycles. The pyrolysis temperature of each preform was 800°C, 900°C, 1000°C and 1100°C (all for 1h and in N₂ atmosphere), respectively. The heating rates of the conventional and microwave sintering were ~7°C/min and ~40°C/min, respectively. The microwave sintering furnace (9kW, 2.45GHz; temperature measured by pyrometer) is manufactured by Changsha Longtai microwave thermal instrument manufacturing Co., Ltd, China. The conventional sintering furnace (6kW) is manufactured by Hunan Dingli Technology Co., Ltd, China.

The flexural strength was characterized by three-point bending at room temperature, with a dimension of 3 mm (B) × 4 mm (H) × 35 mm and crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The fracture toughness was determined with single edge notch beam (SENB) method with a dimension of 3 mm (B) × 6 mm (H) × 45 mm and crosshead speed of 0.05 mm/min. The morphology and microstructure of the specimens was analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI Quanta-200).

3. Results and discussion

The flexural properties of the SiC/SiC composites sintered by conventional and microwave heating from 800°C to 1100°C are listed in Table 1, which indicates that the flexural strength and toughness of the microwave sintered SiC/SiC composites are higher than that of the conventional sintered ones at the same temperature. For example, the flexure strength and toughness of 1100°C-microwave-sintered SiC/SiC composites are 11.5% and 22.6% higher than that of the 1100°C-conventional-sintered ones [13]. Besides, their fracture behaviors and microstructures are also different in some content.

Table 1 Flexural properties of SiC/SiC composites fabricated by microwave and conventional sintering ^[13]

Sintering temperature	Conventional sintering		Microwave sintering	
	Flexure strength (MPa)	Flexure toughness (MPa m ^{1/2})	Flexure strength (MPa)	Flexure toughness (MPa m ^{1/2})
800°C	349.6 ± 24.8	20.5 ± 1.9	425.6 ± 41.3	20.9 ± 2.0
900°C	364.3 ± 33.5	21.3 ± 2.1	465.8 ± 46.2	21.6 ± 2.2
1000°C	441.5 ± 41.7	22.7 ± 2.3	489.9 ± 47.6	25.5 ± 2.4
1100°C	494.8 ± 48.9	24.3 ± 2.4	551.5 ± 51.7	29.8 ± 2.8

The typical load-displacement curves of the conventional and microwave heating sintered SiC/SiC composites are shown in Fig.1, which both exhibit non-brittle

fracture behaviors of ceramics matrix composite, and can be divided into two stages: the linear stage and the nonlinear fluctuating stage.

Fig.1 The typical load-displacement curves of the microwave and conventional heating sintered SiC/SiC composites

In the first stage, micro-cracks are generated in the SiC matrix and the exterior load is transferred from the matrix to the SiC fibers. Fig.2 presents the matrix microstructures on the fracture surface of the 1100°C-conventional-sintered and 1100°C-microwave-sintered SiC/SiC composites. Apparently, resulting from lower heating rates ($\sim 7^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$), the conventional heating sintered SiC/SiC composites have denser matrix with less micro-cracks on the bundle surface (Fig.2 (a) and Fig.2 (b)), which are mostly produced by the subsequent exterior load. In stark contrast, the SiC/SiC composites fabricated by higher microwave heating rate ($\sim 40^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$) have looser matrix with much more micro-cracks on the bundle surface (Fig.2 (c) and Fig.2 (d)) and the micro-cracks are chiefly from the preparation process, but not exterior load.

Fig.2 The typical matrix microstructures on the fiber bundle surface of the (a) (b) 1100°C-conventional-sintered and (c) (d) 1100°C-microwave-sintered SiC/SiC composite

In the second stage, before the sudden fall of load, the curves tend to be fluctuating plateaus around the maximum load, which are mainly caused by crack expanding, crack deflecting and partially fibers pulled-out.

Obviously, the denser matrix of the conventional heating sintered SiC/SiC composites makes the micro-cracks growing into bigger cracks easily and expanding to fibers much earlier (Fig.2 (b)). The loose matrix with more micro-cracks on the fiber bundle surface offer more routines for the cracks expanding and easily deflect the cracks from the fibers (Fig.2 (d)), preventing them from premature breaking and absorb more external energy. Hence, the displacement of the microwave heating

sintered SiC/SiC composites (displacement $\approx 0.65\text{mm}$) is higher than that the conventional heating sintered ones (displacement $\approx 0.5\text{mm}$), meaning that their strain is higher.

Fig.3 The typical matrix microstructures intra the fiber bundles of (a) (c)

1100°C-conventional-sintered and (b) (d) 1100°C-microwave-sintered SiC/SiC composites

The expanding cracks and the micro-cracks produced in the first stage will result in the cracking of the matrix after the local stress exceeding the bearing capacity of the SiC matrix. After the maximum values on the curves, the loads drop to some degree and also have a fluctuation stage. The reason is that the un-fractured SiC fibers bear the exterior load and are pulled out from the matrix until they are all broken.

However, it is worth noticing that the fluctuation stage of the microwave heating sintered SiC/SiC composites is longer than that of the conventional heating sintered ones, which can be explained by different microstructures intra the fiber bundles of the fabricated SiC/SiC composites.

As shown in Fig.3(b) and Fig.3(d), the matrix particle size intra the fiber bundles of the 1100°C-microwave-sintered SiC/SiC composites is smaller than that of the 1100°C-conventional-sintered ones and the matrix is looser too (Fig.3(a) and Fig.3(b)), similarly owing to the rapider microwave heating rates. The smaller matrix particles and the looser matrix also provide more expanding routines and deflect more cracks, postponing the cracks reaching the fibers and the premature breaking of fibers. Therefore, the un-fractured fibers bear the exterior loads for longer time than the conventional heating sintered SiC/SiC composites.

Fig.4 The fracture micrographs of the SiC/SiC composites sintered by conventional heating at (a) 800°C, (b) 900°C, (c) 1000°C and (d) 1100°C

The differences between the conventional and microwave heating sintered SiC/SiC composites are reflected in the fracture micrographs as well, shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5.

Fig.5 The fracture micrographs of the SiC/SiC composites sintered by microwave heating at (a) 800°C, (b) 900°C, (c) 1000°C and (d) 1100°C

The long pulled out fibers could be observed for both kinds of SiC/SiC composites, which are the main reinforcing mechanism of ceramics matrix composites actually [15]. However, by comparing Fig.4 with Fig.5, it can be observed that more chips exist on the fractured surfaces of the microwave sintered SiC/SiC composites. The EDS analysis was measured to investigate whether the chips are external pollutants or not, and the results are listed in Fig.6. In accord with the pyrolysis product of PCS, the chips consist of Si, C and O elements, proving that they were definitively from SiC/SiC composite matrix. Nevertheless, the high ratio of C

atoms (88.59%) can be attributed to two reasons: (1) the high energy electrons may penetrate the chips and the PyC interphase may be detected; (2) the EDS analysis is not a precise quantitative measurement in itself. The chips are from the looser matrix of the microwave heating sintered SiC/SiC composites (Fig.2 (d) and Fig.3 (b) during the fracture process.

Fig.6 The EDS analysis on the chips of the fractured fiber surfaces of the microwave sintered SiC/SiC composites

4. Conclusions

SiC/SiC composites with KD-I SiC fiber as reinforcements and PCS as precursor were fabricated by PIP process using microwave and conventional heating from 800°C to 1100°C. Their different fracture behaviors and microstructures are investigated and discussed. The conclusions could be summarized as follows:

(1) Different sintering heating cause different fracture behaviors of SiC/SiC composites. The microwave heating sintered SiC/SiC composites have higher strain values and wider fluctuating plateaus on the typical load-displacement curves.

(2) The different fracture behaviors are resulted from different microstructures.

The microwave heating sintered SiC/SiC composites have looser matrix with much

more micro-cracks on the fiber bundles, which bringing about the higher strain values of SiC/SiC composites. Meanwhile, the smaller matrix particle size and looser matrix intra the fiber bundles result in wider fluctuating plateaus than the conventional heating sintered ones on the typical load-displacement curves.

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